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RECEPTIVE SKILLS AMONG B.Ed. TRAINEES

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.545956>

Abstract

Language and life are inter-related. The scope of language is widened with the widening scope of human activity. Today there is no activity, which does not find its expression in terms of language. Listening and reading are passive or receptive skills and speaking and writing are active or productive skills. The paper is an attempt to find to identify the receptive skills in English among B.Ed trainees. The investigator adopted the survey method to study receptive skills of B.Ed trainees. The study is based on primary data which is collected from 300 BEd trainees in and around Coimbatore district using simple random sampling technique. The findings reveal that totally 25% of the selected B.Ed. trainees belong to low level of receptive skill, 46.6% of the selected BEd trainees belong to moderate level of receptive skill, 26.6% of the selected BEd trainees belong to high level of receptive skill. Also it is found that there is no significant difference in receptive among the selected B.Ed trainees based on gender and locality.

Keywords: Receptive Skills; B.Ed. Trainees; Education.

Cite This Article: N. Archana, and K. Somasundaram. (2017). "RECEPTIVE SKILLS AMONG B.Ed. TRAINEES." *International Journal of Research - Granthaalayah*, 5(3)SE, 13-17. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.545956>.

1. Introduction

Language and life are inter-related. The scope of language is widened with the widening scope of human activity. Today there is no activity, which does not find its expression in terms of language. Listening and reading are passive or receptive skills and speaking and writing are active or productive skills.

Listening is a complex operation integrating the distinct components of perception and linguistic knowledge. The degree of listening depends on the type of material and its organization, the interest the material holds for the listener, the way it is presented and the emotional state of the listener. Of the time adults spend in communication activities, 45 per cent is devoted to listening, only 30 per cent to speaking, 16 per cent to reading, and a mere 9 per cent to writing (P.T.

Rankin, 1962, p.2).Adrian Doff (1988) talks about the following two types of listening. Casual listening: Many times people listen to something without any particular purpose and without much concentration. This type of listening is found in social contexts. Focussed listening is 'intensive listening' for information or for transacting business. The listener is attentive and concentrates on what the speaker is saying. Teachers should model good listening, especially by giving students full attention and eye contact when they speak (De Hoven, 1983). Both spontaneous speech and written language read orally should be used to teach listening, because different skills are involved (Froese, 1981). Students with learning problems tend to comprehend better when speed of presentation is slower than the normal rate (Blosser, Weidner and Dinero, 1976; Mc Croskey and Thompson, 1973). Because of linguistic problems of some students, teachers should use structurally simple and relatively short sentences of not more than 5 to 10 words in their language of instruction (Wiig and Semel, 1984).

The goal of all reading is the comprehension of meaning. Effective reading includes not only a literal comprehension of an author's word, but also an interpretation of his mood, tone, feeling and attitude (Dechant and Smith, 1977, P. 237).Gray (1967) views that when people read something they understand it at three levels. First, the purely literal responding to the graphic signals only with little depth of understanding, the second level at which the reader recognizes the author's meaning, and the third level where the reader's own personal experiences and judgments influence his response to the text. These three levels can be summarized as "Reading the lines, Reading between the lines and Reading beyond the lines". Many factors may influence the skills of reading. Some of the conditions needed by children to make maximum progress in learning to read are physical and mental health, abilities of visual and auditory recognition, intelligence, background of experience, knowledge of the language, desire to read, purpose for reading, interest in reading, confidence and certain other environmental factors.

2. Research Design

The study aimed to identify the receptive skills in English among B.Ed trainees. In the present study survey method was used. The investigator adopted the survey method to study receptive skills of B.Ed trainees. The study is based on primary data which is collected from 300 BEd trainees in and around Coimbatore district.

Hypothesis: 1

There will be difference in the level of receptive skill among selected B.Ed trainees.

Table 1: Frequency and percentage difference in the level of receptive skill among selected B.Ed trainees

RECEPTIVE SKILL								
Low			Moderate			High		
Q1	F	%	Q2	F	%	Q3	F	%
59	75	25%	74	140	46.6%	86	76	26.33%

Table 1 exhibits the result of receptive skill among the selected B.Ed. trainees. According to the table totally 25% of the selected B.Ed. trainees belong to low level of receptive skill, 46.6% of

the selected BEd trainees belong to moderate level of receptive skill, 26.6% of the selected BEd trainees belong to high level of receptive skill. So the hypothesis No: 1 is accepted. Thus it is inferred that there is a difference in the level of receptive skill among selected B.Ed trainees.

Hypothesis: 2

There will be a significant mean score difference in receptive skills between male and female among selected B.Ed trainees.

Table 2: Means score difference and t-test of receptive skills between male and female among selected B.Ed trainees

S.NO	GENDER	N	Mean	S.D	df	t-value	p-value	Result
1.	MALE	30	76.67	14.423	300	1.916	.372	N.S
2.	FEMALE	270	70.81	16.014				
3.	TOTAL	300						

Table 2 shows that mean score difference in receptive skills between male and female among the selected B.Ed trainees. The calculated t-value is statistically not significant at 0.05 levels and hence, the hypothesis 2 is rejected. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference in receptive skills between male and female among selected B.Ed trainees.

Chart 1: Mean Score Difference in Receptive Skill Based on Gender

Hypothesis: 3

There will be a significant mean score difference in receptive skills between the groups based on locality among selected B.Ed trainees.

Table 3: Means score difference and t-test of receptive skills between the groups based on locality among selected B.Ed trainees

S.NO	LOCALITY	N	Mean	S.D	df	t-value	p-value	Result
1.	RURAL	158	71.77	16.056	300	.419	.789	N.S
2.	URBAN	142	70.99	15.850				
3.	TOTAL	300						

Table 3 shows that mean score difference in receptive skills between the groups based on locality among the selected B.Ed trainees. The calculated t-value is statistically not significant at 0.05 levels and hence, the hypothesis 3 is rejected. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference in receptive skills between the groups based on locality among selected B.Ed trainees.

Chart: 2 Mean Score Difference in Receptive Skill Based on Locality

Conclusion

The findings reveal that totally 25% of the selected B.Ed. trainees belong to low level of receptive skill, 46.6% of the selected BEd trainees belong to moderate level of receptive skill, 26.6% of the selected BEd trainees belong to high level of receptive skill. Also it is found that there is no significant difference in receptive among the selected B.Ed trainees based on gender and locality.

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